

**THE ISSUE OF TRANSITION TO "GREEN" ECONOMY AND ITS
IMPORTANCE**

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Master's student of Tashkent State Law University, majoring in environmental law and sustainable development and destroyed natural resources on the earth have exceeded the natural resources used by humans from the time of its appearance until now. .

In recent years, environmental problems: climate change, desertification, loss of biodiversity, depletion of natural resources, increasing poverty, lack of fresh water, food, energy, people and countries Problems such as inequality between the two are proof that the current economic systems are not perfect. Global crises, climate change, air pollution, loss of flora and fauna, increasing demand for water and other natural resources deepen the current socio-economic problems of stability in both developed and developing countries. The image of the current world, irreparable environmental disasters and huge damage to the environment requires the need to transition to a "green economy". The world's leading countries have already started the transition to a green economy. They have realized that green economy is not a substitute for sustainable development but is a way to achieve sustainable development.

and well-being no less than them .

Most studies, literature and research show that today's problems such as resource scarcity, environmental problems and economic risks can only be solved by transitioning to a green economy.

of the "green economy" were studied by foreign economists and scientists William Hynes, Shannon Wang, Erik Solheim, Patricia, Ardakanian, Dirk Jaeger.

TV Zakharova, Valentin Pchelintsev, Tatyana Kruglikova, Irina Zhivotovskaya, Tatyana Chernomorova, Tkachenko Aleksandr Alexandrovich and other scientists from the representatives of the CIS emphasized the necessity of transition to a green economy and its high impact on the country's development.

Green economy is an economic system aimed at reducing the resources necessary for human life and health, environmental risks and environmental scarcity, and developing all sectors of the economy without damaging the environment . Green economy can be associated with ecological economy , but it is a new trend that is more politically applied.

Resource scarcity is the lack of resources that serve to satisfy human needs throughout life. Scarcity of resources is an age-old and unsolved problem of humanity, and the disproportion between unlimited human needs and limited resources is considered the main problem of the economy. I can give an example of water shortage, depletion of underground and surface resources, food shortage, limited number of working population, lack of energy resources and others. Some resources can be regenerated. For example, a new garden can be created by replanting trees instead of felled trees. Even if it takes years. But minerals are non-renewable resources.

As we know from history, after the Industrial Revolution, there was a lack of respect for natural resources. The reason is that the more industrialized the country is, the more developed the production, the more diversified the economy, the greater the demand for natural resources and raw materials. As a result, the environment is seriously damaged. The better the standard of living of people , the more developed the country, know that this country has brought a lot of things from nature and caused damage accordingly. This thought was true of many developed and industrialized countries of the world about 30 years ago , but now they have searched for and developed environmentally friendly ways of

development. This is reflected in the closely related concepts of economy, politics and ecology. Sustainable development, use of renewable energy sources, investment in ecological technologies, "Green economy" are among them.

In the next two hundred years, the number of consumers on Earth increased 5 times, but the land surface and natural resources did not increase. Climate change is also on the rise. 72% of the Earth's surface is oceans, and several parts of the land are uninhabitable. Addressing such problems must be accompanied by strategies that promote economic growth, meet various social needs such as education, health, social protection and job creation, while combating environmental pollution. and the need to study climate change has become a strategic goal of "Green Economy".

Green growth is a special strategy for sustainable development. The strategy provides a way to combat environmental problems and the use of natural resources.

and legal bases of the transition to "green economy" are expressed in most of the Earth's strategic development documents. The analysis shows that "Green Economy" is not used as a basic concept or a priority in ensuring sustainable development on Earth. Nevertheless, "Green economy" is considered as one of the ways of integrating the priorities of ensuring sustainable development, including employment and green development, measures to combat climate change.

The United Nations (UN) launched the Green Economy Initiative in 2008. The main goal of this initiative was recognized as "sustainable development and eradication of poverty, achieving sustainable development". UN experts say that the goal of the transition to a green economy is "green investments" in economic sectors and the social sphere. encourage the direction of these investments, which are important economic resources, natural capital and ecosystems, using relatively efficient methods, or help to replace them with other alternative resources when they are depleted.

The UN Environment Division has developed a practical definition of a green economy, one that improves human well-being and social equity while significantly reducing environmental risk and environmental scarcity.

In recent years, the concept of "Green Economy" has emerged as a strategic priority for many governments and intergovernmental organizations. In total, 65 countries have developed Green Economy and related strategies. They will be prepared to address the major challenges of the 21st century , from resource scarcity to climate change and economic volatility.

A green economy will bring prosperity to the people of the earth and reduce the level of poverty, a high level of human development in countries, whether it is in the field of education or health care, in short, what is necessary for a person to live a prosperous life. 'Isha serves to create the possibility of achieving it, helps to restore biodiversity, serves to prevent negative changes in ecology and protect the environment, attracts investments in the economic, social and ecological sphere and directs them to effective use.

To sum up , there is a need to form a "Green Economy" in the conditions of limited resources and negative consequences of environmental problems. The transition to the "green economy" allows for efficient use of resources, ensuring ecological balance, creating new jobs, and ensuring sustainable economic growth. Therefore, there is an urgent need to switch to an economic model that increases human well-being, conserves resources, and ensures that future generations are not exposed to serious environmental risks.

